

Job Security Perception of Remote Workers in Turkey

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Abstract

This study was conducted to determine whether remote working triggers an increase in job insecurity in Turkey. Qualitative and quantitative research methods were applied in the study. In this study, a mixed-method approach, combining qualitative and quantitative research methods, was adopted. The quantitative method was implemented to measure the perception of job security among remote workers. To enhance the reliability of the findings, qualitative methods were also utilized. In the quantitative method, 235 people working in the private sector having experience in teleworking were selected as a sample. Data were collected by the questionnaire method. Structural equation modeling was used to analyze the data. The qualitative method selected

twenty people working as experts and managers having prior experience on remote working as a sample. The content analysis method was used to analyze the data. Organizations aspiring to gain a competitive advantage should consider flexible working models and the concept of job security and implement the assured flexibility model. In this respect, they ought to implement the necessary human resources policies to ensure that employees have positive perceptions of their job security.

Keywords: Flexible Work, Job Security, Labor Market, Remote Work, Remote Workers.

JEL Codes: J100, J10, J00

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1. Introduction

Since the 1970s, job insecurity has risen due to preferred economic policies, rising unemployment rates, and changing working models (Green, 2003). In a survey conducted by the PWC, more than half of the employees stated that their workload had increased at the workplace, and that they experienced uncertainties regarding job security and financial difficulties (PWC, 2019). At the same time, the surge in the number of self-employed, non-standard working models has also led to a rise in precariousness (ILO, 2024). On the other hand, increasing job insecurity, especially with the COVID-19 pandemic and the fear of unemployment throughout the world, adversely affects physical and mental health (Green, 2020). Despite a decrease in job insecurity in 2024, due to economic developments in remote work and the increase in artificial intelligence, it can be said that employees still feel precarious due to economic conditions. In universal perspective, the job insecurity rate is 18% in China, 25% in India, less than 20% in Canada, 24% in the USA, and 18% in Chile.

Concurrently, the recession in the Netherlands and economic difficulties in the UK have prevented workers from being secure (ADP, 2024). The loss of job security causes workers' future employment rates to fall and their wages to remain low (Jarosch, 2021). Job insecurity also leads to family conflicts (Richter, 2011).

Accordingly, job security comes to the fore in the context of decent work, which has gained importance with the change in how work is conducted and working models. Today especially, the fact that work can be executed anywhere in the world can bring with it the precarious dimension regarding the working conditions.

2. Literature

Globalization, urbanization, and technological advances have changed human resource practices since the 1980s. Since the late twentieth century, the traditional employer-employee relationship has been replaced by the concept of precarity and non-standard working arrangements characterized by precarious work (Kiran, et al., 2022).

Job insecurity has gained importance, and many studies have been conducted based on job insecurity due to changes in economic systems and an increase in temporary contracts. At the same time, the increase in remote working arising from the COVID-19 pandemic has made the job insecurity even more prominent. Teleworking is a form of work organized and performed using information technology in the context of an employment contract/relationship, performed at the employer's workplace (ILO, 2020). Changes in working models also increase job insecurity. In the Sverke and Hellgren

Model of job insecurity, the employment contract, labor market characteristics, and uncertainties are considered objective conditions. In this context, it can be stated that individuals who find themselves in employment types and organizations classified as precarious experience more job insecurity than individuals enjoying a 'more secure' type of employment (Sverke et al., 2006).

Job security can be perceived as a threat to the future continuity of a profession, or it can be defined as an involuntary, basic perception of job loss depending on the potential and subjective perception of the continuity of the current job (Witte, 2005). Job insecurity can be defined as the threat that people feel regarding their jobs, the powerlessness they feel concerning the pursuing of the job and feeling threatened in general (Greenhalgh et al., 1984). According to another definition, job insecurity is the personal experience of facing the threat of losing a job or its valuable features (Khawli, et al., 2022). As can be perceived from the definitions, job insecurity is a concept affiliated with an individual's perception. This concept is affected by the labor market conditions as well as the country's economic conditions.

On the other hand, it has been determined in the literature that different factors affect the concept of job insecurity. Demographic, individual, cultural, and work organization related factors are among them (Selvi et al., 2017). Although it is a concept that stringent upon different factors and employees' perceptions, organizations consisting of employees with a perception of job security are advantageous in achieving competitive edge. Research conducted by Karakılıç (2023) reveals that there are statistically significant relationships between the job security variables and performance variables. Although only a few studies examine the relationship between remote work and jobs, it is possible to come across studies on the effects of remote work. In a study conducted on remote workers during the COVID-19 pandemic, decreased productivity, emotional burnout, job insecurity, work-related stress and intense burnout, physical and emotional burden, psychological fatigue, emotional pressures, and the excessive workload it brings with it heightened professional burnout (Costin et al., 2023). Another study on remote working during the COVID-19 pandemic found that employees perceived remote working negatively. Accordingly, employees caught in the COVID-19 pandemic still had to work remotely to perform their duties since they were concerned about job insecurity and lack of social protection (Wontorczyk et al., 2022). Another study similarly found that telecommuting contributed to job insecurity in the COVID-19 pandemic and that there is a strong, statistically significant, and positive correlation among these aspects (Nemteanu & Dabja, 2023). Lim (2020) found that individuals with a higher perception of job insecurity would prefer remote work less than

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those who perceive it as less advantageous for themselves and their organizations. In another study on teleworking, although positive outcomes such as providing flexibility to labor markets, reducing costs, contributing to the improvement of environmental conditions, preventing time loss, increasing productivity, and work-life balance were identified, negative results such as failure to achieve a work-life balance, difficulty in unionization, limited career opportunities, lack of social security and job security, occupational health and safety problems were also identified (Metin & Yıldız, 2021).

Another study on teleworking during the COVID-19 pandemic argues that employer surveillance and demands for workers to be accessible by employers increased. Although advancements in IT technology have allowed workers to continue to work away from the employer's workplace, for some teleworkers, the fact that work can be conducted from anywhere raises concerns regarding job security and that the work can be conducted by anyone (ILO, 2021).

In a study on the negative effects of remote working on job insecurity, work-life conflict, and employee behavior, Nemteanu & Dabija (2023) found that remote working during the pandemic period contributed to job insecurity, work-life conflict, and professional isolation.

In a study conducted by Radu et al. (2024) on how teleworking is perceived and its effects on psychological safety and job performance, a positive rela-

tionship was revealed, particularly in regard to teleworking and job performance. Investigating whether the effects of remote work affect job satisfaction performance, Jamaludin and Kamal (2023) revealed that job satisfaction increased with the perception of autonomy of remote work. In a study on the effects of job insecurity on job performance and alienation of full-time hospitality and tourism sector employees, Abouelenien et al. (2024) found a positive relationship between job insecurity and alienation and a negative relationship between job insecurity and performance. In another study on the subjective perception of job insecurity in Italy in the pandemic period, it was found that worsening household economic conditions, increasing the number of employees at home, having a temporary contract, and working in the private sector were also associated with increased job insecurity (Nappo et al.2023).

Although there is no individual study in the literature on the perception of job security of remote workers, it can be said that the existing studies are generally concerned with the results of remote working. The results of the studies reveal that remote work leads to job insecurity. On the other hand, there are studies on job security and the perceptions of remote workers. No study was found, and temporary work was found to be related to job insecurity. This study used qualitative and quantitative methods to reveal the direct relationship between remote work and job insecurity.

2.1. Research Model-Hypothesis and Research Questions

Figure 1. Research Model

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

H1: There is a relationship between the positive attitude dimension of teleworking and the perception of job security.

H2: There is a relationship between the skill development dimension of teleworking and the perception of job security.

H3: There is a relationship between the resistance to negative attitudes dimension of teleworking and the perception of job security.

H4: There is a relationship between the organizational support dimension of teleworking and the perception of job security.

Figure 1 illustrates the hypotheses of the structural equation model. Structural equation modeling was used to test these hypotheses in the study. Structural equation modeling is a multivariate statistical method that estimates parameters for a system of simultaneous equations (Stein, 2012). At the same time, this method is directed toward theoretical constructs represented nby latent factors (Hox.et al.,2017). The Table1 depicting the fit of the collect-

ed data with the model is given below. Accordingly, GFI, RMSEA, AGFI, CFI, and NFI values are within the ideal fit value ranges and, therefore, the model is valid. At the same time, the chi-square/sd value showing the model's fit was found to be 2.14. The chi-square's degrees of freedom being less than three indicates that the model's overall fit is accepT-able.

Table 1. Fit Indices

Fit of the model		
GFI	0.90 ≤ GFI- 0.85≤GFI	0.90
AGFI	0.90 ≤ AGFI-0.85≤AGFI	0.86
RMSEA	RMSEA≤0.05- RMSEA≤0.08	0.06
NFI	0.95≤NFI -0.90≤NFI	0.95
NNFI	0.95≤NNFI -0.90≤NNFI	0.96
IFI	0.95≤IFI -0.90≤IFI	0.97
CFI	0.97≤CFI -0.95≤CFI	0.97

Source: (Karagöz, 2019).

This study was conducted to determine whether telecommuting causes an increase in job insecurity. In line with this purpose, the study sought answers to the following:

- How remote workers perceive the right to job security in their organizations,
- How remote workers are dismissed in their organizations,
- Whether remote workers are subject to arbitrary dismissal in their organizations.

3. Materials and Methods

3.1. Research Methodology

A mixed method research in which qualitative and quantitative methods are used together was deemed appropriate as a research model. Mixed method research is research through which the data collected by different methods are brought together and compared, thereby increasing the credibility of the results. In this research design, qualitative and quantitative data of equal importance have been collected simultaneously and analyzed using different methods. In the last stage, the similarities and differences between the findings are compared and interpreted (Harrison et al., 2020). Accordingly, in this study, the data obtained from the job security and remote working scale were analyzed using the quantitative research method, and the data obtained from the semi-structured interview form on job security perception were analyzed using the qualitative research method. Ethics approval for the research was

obtained from the Tokat Gaziosmanpaşa University Social and Human Sciences Research Ethics Board. Participants were informed about the research and its confidential conduct.

3.2. Participants

The quantitative part of the study group consists of 235 people who have worked remotely in the private sector. At this stage, the convenience sampling method, one of the non-random sampling methods was used. The convenient sampling method covers the sample elements that the researcher can conveniently access and is implemented in cases where it is difficult to access the samples (Monette et al., 2005). While calculating the sample size, the qualifications of structural equation modeling regarding sample size were considered. Ding et al. (1995) state that the sample size should be 100-150 in a study to be estimated with the maximum likelihood estimator. The sample of 235 people formed for this study was sufficient in this respect . The study group of the qualitative part of the research consisted of twenty people having prior experiences in the private sector. The qualitative study group was formed separately from the quantitative study group. In qualitative research, small groups that can provide detailed data corresponding to the research purpose are formed instead of large groups. The depth of these small groups' data will contribute to the research (Patton, 2005). The qualitative study group in this direction was formed using the typical case sampling method. Typical case sampling refers to

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groups containing information that can explain the event or phenomenon under consideration among many similar in the universe (Marshall & Rossman, 2006). Demographic data regarding the study sample groups are given in Table 2 in the Findings Sec-

tion. Accordingly, 65% of the participants worked as managers and 35% as experts. While 70% of the participants had eleven years of experience or more, 20% had six to ten years of experience, and 5% had one to five years of experience.

Table 2. Demographic Data

Fit of the model			
Participants	Demographic Characteristics	Total	
Experience	1-5 years	4	20
	6-10 years	20	
	11 years and above	14	
Title	Manager and Administrator	16	20
	Expert	4	

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

3.3. Data Collection Tools

Two different scales were used to collect the study's quantitative data. These were the remote working attitude scale and the job security perception scale. In the qualitative data collection phase of the study, the researcher developed a semi-structured interview form. The remote working scale is the scale developed by Başol and Çömlekçi (2022); a 'Validity-reliability study of a remote working attitude scale.' The factor loads of the items in the scale are between 0.698 and 0.909, and the total variance explained is 80.39%. According to the results of confirmatory factor analysis, the distance working attitude scale (Chi-square/freedom value: 2.17; RMSEA: 0.06; NFI: 0.97; NNFI: 0.98; CFI: 0.99; GFI: 0.92 and AGFI: 0.89) consists of four factors and sixteen items. The scale's internal consistency was calculated as 0.91, and the item-total correlations were between 0.330 and 0.812. It was prepared on a 5-point scale, where 1 is strongly disagree and 5 is strongly agree. The perception of the job security scale was taken from Yilmaz's (2020) unpublished doctoral dissertation, 'The Mediating Effect of Organizational Opposition on the Relationship between Classroom Teachers' Perceptions of Job Security and Professional Self-esteem.' It consists of six questions and a 5-point Likert scale applied. The terms strongly disagree, disagree, undecided, agree, and strongly agree were used.

3.4. Job Security Perception Semi-structured Interview Form

A literature review was conducted creating the open-ended questions in the semi-structured in-

terview form. The nine-question semi-structured interview form was presented to eight field experts. At this stage, the content and face validity of the semi-structured interview form was analyzed. Lawshe's (1975) technique was used for the content and face validity (Elçi & Uzunboylu, 2020). In the Lawshe technique, six steps were followed: 1. forming a group of field experts; 2. I am preparing the candidate form; 3. obtaining expert opinions; 4. obtaining content validity ratios; 5. obtaining content validity indices; 6. forming the final form according to the content validity ratios/index criteria. Expert opinions for each question in the semi-structured interview form are graded as the question measures the targeted construct, and the question is related to the construct. However, it should be improved, as the question does not measure the targeted construct. The Lawshe content validity rate calculation was used to calculate the content validity rates of the questions. Eight experts' minimum content validity criterion (CVR) is 0.78 (Yeşilyurt; Çapraz, 2018). $KGO = \frac{NuN}{2} - 1$ or $KGO = \frac{Nu-N}{2N/2}$ Nu in the formula indicates the number of experts who say the question measures the targeted construct, and N indicates the number of experts who expressed an opinion. The calculated content validity rate is given in Table 3. The CGI value obtained from the semi-structured interview form with the opinions of eight experts was 0.91. This value is above the content validity criterion of 0.78. Questions 4, 6, and 7 were rearranged in line with expert opinions. A semi-structured interview form consisting of three questions concerning demographic information and nine open-ended questions regarding the scope of the research was used.

Table 3. Content Validity Rate

Question	The question measures the targeted construct	The question is related to the structure but should be improved	The question does not measure the targeted construct	KGO
1	8	0	0	1.00
2	8	0	0	1.00
3	8	0	0	1.00
4	7	1	0	0.75
5	8	0	0	1.00
6	7	1	0	0.75
7	7	1	0	0.75
8	8	0	0	1.00
9	8	0	0	1.00
Total Number of Experts: eight				
Content validity measure (CVM): 0.78				
Content Validity Index (CVI):0.91				

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

3.5. Data Collection

Interviews were conducted digitally or one-on-one by phone. They were conducted in July 2025. The interviews each lasted for approximately 25-30 minutes.

3.6. Data Analysis

The Content Analysis method was used to analyze the study's qualitative data. Content analysis provides a detailed analysis of the data obtained and reaches the concept categories and themes that explain these data. In content analysis, codes are extracted from events and phenomena frequently repeated in the data set or emphasized by the

participants, from codes to categories and from categories to themes. These data are depicted in Table 4. Data (codes) that are found to be related to each other are interpreted by going from specific to general within the framework of certain concepts (categories) and themes (Bengtsson, 2016). In this direction, the responses of the remote workers to the semi-structured interview form were coded separately by an expert and a researcher by creating a coding key. The reliability of the data was calculated using Mileess and Huberman's (1994) Reliability Formula, which resulted from the coding made by two people. Reliability = consensus / (consensus + disagreement) reliability coefficient was 0.94. The result obtained here was considered reliable.

Table 4. The Reliability of Job Security Perception

Article	Code	Category	Theme
1	2	2	1
2	2	2	2
3	2	2	1
4	2	2	2
5	2	2	2
6	2	2	2
7	2	2	1
8	2	2	2
9	2	2	2

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

4. Results

Demographic information regarding the participants is presented in Table 5. Accordingly, 57% of the participants were female and 43% were male. While 66% of the participants worked in domestic companies, 34% worked in international companies. In respect to analyzing the seniority of the participants, 40% had been working for more than sixteen years, 31% between eleven and fifteen years, 18% between six and ten years, and 11% for five years or less. Regarding education level, 9% of the par-

ticipants had a PhD, 24% had a master's degree, 55% had a bachelor's degree, 9% had an associate's degree, and 3% had a high school diploma. 21% of the participants worked in education, 15% in technology, 10% in retail, 9% in textiles, 7% in banking and finance, and 5% in manufacturing. 34% worked in sectors other than these. When the titles of the participants are analyzed, 43% were experts responsible, 28% were managers, 18% were managers/chefs/assistant managers, and 11% were assistants/personnel/assistant specialists.

Table 5. Descriptive Findings Regarding the Participants

Group	Frequency (f)	Percentage %
Gender		
Female	135	57.4
Male	100	42.6
Business Type		
National	156	66.4
International	79	33.6
Seniority (Years)		
16 ≥	95	40.4
11-15	72	30.6
6-10	42	17.9
5 ≤	26	11.1
Educational Status		
License	130	55.3
Master's Degree	57	24.3
Associate Degree	22	9.4
PhD	20	8.5
High School	6	2.5
Sector		
Education	49	20.9
Technology-Information Processing	34	14.5
Retail	24	10.2
Textile	20	8.5
Banking - Finance	17	7.2
Production - Manufacturing	11	4.7
Other	80	34.0
Title		
Expert-Responsible	102	43.4
Director	65	27.6
Manager-Chief-Deputy Manager	42	17.9
Assistant-staff-assistant specialist	26	11.0
Total*	235	100

*is the sum of each group

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

Figure 2. Structural Equation Model
Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

The hypothesis values of the research model are shown in Figure 2. There are findings regarding the relationship between job security perception and

positive attitude, skill development, resistance to negative attitude, and corporate support dimensions. Table 6 includes the evaluation of the Research

Table 6. Evaluation of Research Hypotheses, AVE, and Construct Validity Findings

Factors/Statements	Lambda (λ)	t-value	R2	AVE	Building Reliability
Positive Attitude (PA)	0,91	18,02	0,828	0,842	0,955
	0,88	17,05	0,774		
	0,94	19,23	0,883		
	0,94	18,90	0,883		
Skill Development (SD)	0,77	13,77	0,592	0,629	0,870
	0,90	17,21	0,810		
	0,84	15,66	0,705		
	0,64	10,59	0,409		
Resistance to Negative Attitudes (RNA)	0,77	13,47	0,592	0,590	0,849
	0,94	18,18	0,883		
	0,66	11,02	0,435		
Corporate Support (CS)	0,67	11,12	0,448	0,792	0,938
	0,90	17,56	0,810		
	0,89	17,28	0,792		
	0,90	17,62	0,810		
	0,87	16,71	0,756		

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	0,72	9,71	0,518	0,767	0,819
	0,88	13,01	0,880		
Perception of Job Security (PJS)	0,80	11,91	0,800		
	0,77	11,43	0,770		
	0,87	12,96	0,870		
H1 : PA → PJS	0,33	1,77*	Supported		
H2 : SD→ PJS	-0,21	-1,08	Rejected		
H3 : RNA→ PJS	0,18	1,72*	Supported		
H4 : CS →PJS	-0,00	-0,04	Rejected		
* $p < 0.100$ ($t > 1.65$)					

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

Hypotheses, AVE and construct validity findings. In light of the data obtained, the following can be said:

H1: There is a relationship between the positive attitude dimension of teleworking and the perception of job security. There is a significant relationship, and the hypothesis is accepted.

H2: There is a relationship between the skill development dimension of teleworking and the perception of job security. The hypothesis is rejected.

H3: There is a relationship between the resistance to negative attitudes dimension of teleworking and the perception of job security. There is a significant relationship, and the hypothesis is accepted.

H4: There is a relationship between the organizational support dimension of teleworking and the perception of job security. The hypothesis is rejected.

5. Qualitative Method Findings

This section includes the responses of the research participants to the questions in the semi-structured interview form.

Table 7 shows the participants' views on the concept of job security. According to the study, 65% of the participants worked as managers and 35% as experts. While 50% of the participants had sixteen years of experience or more, 25% had eleven to fifteen years of experience, 20% had six to ten years of experience, and 5% had one to five years of experience. Both managers and experts expressed the concept as giving legal rights, not being arbitrarily dismissed unfairly, and not experiencing the fear of dismissal. In addition, the managers also expressed that the protection of legal rights meant job security.

Sample statements of the participants are as follows;

Table 7. Meaning of Job Security

Category	Theme	Total %
For Managers	Protection of legal rights	14
	No unjustified arbitrary dismissal	4
	No fear of dismissal	2
	Granting legal rights	1
From the Experts' Perspective	Granting legal rights	2
	No unjustified arbitrary dismissal	1
	No fear of dismissal	1

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

P1: Protection of workers' legal rights in a sustainable environment.

P2: It is the person not unfairly dismissed.

P3: Regulations were made to ensure the worker's protection and regularity.

Table 8. shows the participants' views on their job security rights in their organization. It has been determined that managers and experts have the right to job security, and those who do not.

Sample statements of the participants are as follows:

Table 8. Right to Job Security

Category	Theme	Total %
For Managers	I have job security	14
	I have no job security	2
From the Experts' Perspective	I have job security	3
	I have no job security	1

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

P11: If you make a proper impression and do your job correctly and on time, you have job security.

P12: There is no job security. They think they have rights in the exits made by giving them compensation.

P13: Employment contract can be terminated under any circumstances. Therefore, it is possible to be dismissed at any time.

Table 9. Exit Process

Category	Theme	Total %
For Managers	By mutual agreement	7
	Giving the employer termination rights	3
	Warning-warning exit	3
	Exit as a last resort	2
	Termination during the trial period	1
From the Experts' Perspective	Giving the employer termination rights	3
	By mutual agreement	1

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

Table 9 shows the participants' views on the exit procedures in their organizations. Both managers and experts stated that the termination is by mutual agreement, and the employer gives the right to terminate. Managers also stated they would exit after warning and disciplinary processes, exit as a last resort, and terminate during probation.

Sample statements of the participants are as follows:

P10: If there is a just cause, they can dismiss. Generally, dismissals are made by mutual agreement to protect the company.

P14: Verbal and written warnings are given; if there is no improvement after warnings, the employee is dismissed.

P15: It is a last-applied solution; usually, an attempt is made to save them.

Table 10. Dismissal from Employment with Valid Reason in the Organization

Category	Theme	Total %
For Managers	No dismissal without a just cause	14
	Dismissal without cause is available	2
From the Experts' Perspective	No dismissal without just cause	2
	Dismissal without cause is available	2

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

Table 10 sheds light on the evaluations of the participants of the study regarding dismissals without giving a reason or for non-valid reasons in the organization they work in. Among the managers and experts, a few stated that there were no dismissals without a valid reason, and others stated that there were dismissals without a valid reason.

Sample statements of the participants are as follows:

P3: One of our employers dismissed a friend from the planning department, who was also young, for reasons related to his personal life. He was a friend who did his job correctly. He was dismissed without a reason, saying I do not want to work with you anymore.

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P4: There can be dismissals for absurd reasons, such as our friend in the call center responding late to a call, missing an incoming call, or the low price.

P2: There were no dismissals for non-valid reasons. They prioritized the people they wanted to dismiss.

Table 11. Arbitrary Dismissal of a Person

Category	Theme	Total %
For Managers	My arbitrary dismissal without giving a reason	14
	I am arbitrarily dismissed without cause	2
From the Experts' Perspective	My arbitrary dismissal without giving a reason	2
	I am arbitrarily dismissed without cause	2
		80
		20

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

Table 11 presents the participants' evaluations regarding the possibility of being arbitrarily dismissed without giving a reason in their organization. Among the managers and experts, a number thought that they would not be dismissed without a valid reason, and others thought they could be dismissed without a valid reason.

Sample statements of the participants are as follows:

P14: I have proven myself to my managers and employer with my work discipline in all the companies I have worked in.

P15: I can be dismissed without a valid reason due to the ego problems of the top managers in our office.

P17: I am not dismissed without a valid reason.

Table 12. Fear of Unemployment

Category	Theme	Total %
For Managers	I have no fear of unemployment	14
	Executive - sourced from top management	1
	Due to the economic situation	1
From the Experts' Perspective	I have no fear of unemployment	2
	Because of my lack of self-development	1
	Due to the economic situation	1
		80
		20

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

Table 12 shows the participants' views on the fear of being unemployed in their organization. Managers and experts stated that they had no fear of being unemployed and that they had a fear of being made unemployed due to the economic situation. Managers also feared being unemployed due to reasons arising from managers and senior management. In contrast, the experts feared being made unemployed due to a lack of self-development.

Sample statements of the participants are as follows:

P5: In case the company is sold, organizational changes may come to the agenda, and downsizing may occur in cases of financial problems.

P6: I can leave my company because of the economy. The world is generally subject to stagnant downsizing.

P7: Changes in senior management cause changes, especially in the management team, so I am afraid of being made unemployed.

Table 13. The Relationship Between the Exit Process and Performance

Category	Theme	Total %
For Managers	Performance is not a factor in the decision to quit	7
	Performance influences the decision on dismissal	6
	Rarely dismissed as a result of performance	3
From the Experts' Perspective	Performance influences the decision on dismissal	3
	Performance is not a factor in the decision to quit	1
		80
		20

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

Table 13 shows the participants' views on the relationship between the performance of the employees in the organization they work for and their dismissal status. Both managers and experts believe that performance is effective in the decision of dismissal, as well as those who believe that performance is ineffective. In addition, a number of managers stated that dismissals rarely occur due to performance.

Sample statements of the participants are as follows:

P2: Performance mainly affects the raised rate; I have not come across any dismissals due to performance; employees are gained by providing necessary feedback and training.

P11: Performance studies are not conducted; sometimes evaluations are made for show.

P12: Dismissals are not always based on performance. Sometimes, people who perform exceptionally well can also be dismissed.

Table 14. Dismissal Compliance with Labor Law

Category	Theme	Total %	
For Managers	Dismissals are made in compliance with the Labor Law	15	80
	Dismissals are not carried out in compliance with the Labor Law	1	
From the Experts' Perspective	Dismissals are made in compliance with the Labor Law	4	20

Source(s): Prepared by the Authors

Table 14 presents the participants' views on the compliance of the dismissals in their organizations with the Labor Law. Among the managers and experts were those who stated that the dismissals complied with the labor law and those who stated that they were not in compliance with the labor law.

Sample statements of the participants are as follows:

P3: It is easy to comply with the labor law.

P4: It is sometimes not complied with, but generally, it is behaved appropriately.

P5: It is often by the law, but there are exceptions.

6. Discussion

Four different hypotheses were formulated in the quantitative part of the research. Hypotheses 1 and 3 were accepted, while hypotheses 2 and 4 were rejected. Based on the accepted hypotheses, it can be said that remote workers' perceptions and attitudes regarding the remote work model influence their perception of job security. If remote workers have positive work attitudes, their perception of job security is positively affected, and if not, their perception is negatively affected. A study has also shown that working in virtual teams more effectively using remote work increases their perception of psychological safety and reduces job insecurity (Demirbağ et al., 2021). The study also reveals that the transition to remote work affects the perception of job quality but not job security (Pereira, et al., 2024). This result can be explained by the differences in demographic, organizational, and social variables among the participants.

According to the quantitative method data, a positive relationship was found between the positive attitudes of teleworking experience, including job satisfaction, professional development, motivation,

performance, and skills, and the perception of job security. On the other hand, a positive relationship was also found between the dimensions of telecommuting, which creates stress, negatively affects psychology, disrupts work-life balance, and affects physical health and job insecurity. Similarly, in a study conducted for public institutions, a positive and significant effect of telecommuting experience on job security, job flexibility, organizational performance, and general productivity of employees was determined; it was determined that the perception of job security is a situation that emerges as a result of the employee's evaluation of him/herself regardless of the organization. At the same time, it has been revealed that working styles also affect this perception (Khodaparasti, 2023).

In the qualitative research, managers and experts expressed job security as protecting legal rights, not being unfairly and arbitrarily dismissed, not experiencing fear of dismissal, and being given legal rights. Similarly, in the literature, job security is the perception of employees that their job or an essential part of the job is safe. Although this perception seems subjective, it is measured by asking about the possibility or fear of losing their job in a specific reference period (Burchell, 2022).

It can be seen that both managers and experts participating in the research generally have job security in the organization they work for. It has been determined that they have no fear of unemployment, but this may be possible due to economic conditions or managerial changes. Similarly, Mola et al. (2018) found that 73.6% of employees were satisfied with the stability and job security they perceived at work, while 26.2% were undecided and not satisfied with job security. A study with teachers working in the public sector revealed that job security was present (Yilmaz & Aydin, 2023). In a different study conduct-

ed on employees with German standard employment, it was found that East Germans generally have a lower perception of job security due to their decreased trust in the information policies of their employers (Bernhardt et al., 2014).

The managers and experts who participated in the research stated that the dismissal processes were by mutual agreement, and in case of termination by the employer, their rights were given. Managers also stated that dismissal was made after warnings, dismissal was made as a last resort, and dismissal was made with termination during the probationary period. On the other hand, the termination process of the employment contract varied according to the labor legislation of the countries. In Uzbekistan, in order to terminate an employment contract, there must be a written termination and an agreement must be reached with the union committee; in certain cases, the employer can use the right of termination on its initiative for a number of workers, in a few cases, instead of the right of termination, the condition of placing the worker in another job must be complied with, disciplinary sanctions must be taken into account in dismissals, and the right to preferential dismissal must be observed in worker reductions (Soyipov, 2024). In France, on the other hand, it can be seen that with the reform made in 2008, resignations by agreement have increased. (Batut & Maurin, 2020). However, the exit process in Poland can terminate fixed and indefinite-term employment contracts for just cause (<https://www.legal500.com/guides/wp-content/uploads/sites/1/2024/03/employment-poland.pdf>,2).

According to Turkish Labor Law, the employer's reason for termination of employment needs to be valid or justified. The legal consequences of termination for justified or valid reasons differ. While an employer who dismisses an employee by Article 25/2 for justified reasons does not pay severance and notice pay to the employee, he/she has to pay severance and notice pay or run the notice period for the dismissals for valid reasons (<https://www.mevzuat.gov.tr/MevzuatMetin/1.5.4857-20140910.pdf>).

Managers and experts who participated in the research stated that there is generally no dismissal without a valid reason/without giving a reason in the organizations they work in. On the other hand, in EU countries, there are countries where the employer is obliged to provide a valid reason for dismissal, and there are countries, for example Greece, where there is no obligation to provide a valid reason for dismissal (Papadopoulos, 2022). In Turkish labor law, reasons arising from the employee's behavior and incompetence and reasons arising from the workplace and the enterprise are considered valid. The valid reason requirement is a condition introduced to prevent arbitrary dismissals.

While the managers who participated in the research generally think they will not be dismissed ar-

bitrarily, it has been determined that some believe they can be dismissed arbitrarily among the experts and those who do not. In the study conducted on the subject, it was revealed that unfair dismissals without justifying dismissals will turn into a desire to take revenge in court and may negatively affect the financial status and performance of organizations (Ezeabaogu et al.,2019).

It can be said that the managers and experts who participated in the research generally do not experience fear of unemployment. Nevertheless, it is observed that the fear of unemployment has been on the rise since 2008 across Europe. It has been found that fear of unemployment is related to individuals' perceptions of the economic situation, household income, employers' perceptions of employment in the coming months, and consumer expectations (Blanchflower & Bryson, 2022). Among the managers and experts who participated in the research, it was determined that a number associate the reasons for dismissal with performance, while others do not. Supporting the study's findings, Mohammed (2021) found a weak relationship between termination of the employment contract and performance evaluation in a study conducted on private hospitals. This situation can be explained by a lack of a performance appraisal system in the organizations where the participants in the study work or a lack of fair implementation.

The managers and experts participating in the research generally believe that the dismissals in their organizations are under the Labor Law. Contrary to the research findings, a study conducted in Turkey found that layoffs do not comply with the Labor Law (Yeyin, 1998). However, the research was conducted before the current Labor Law enacted in 2003. In 2003, a job security clause was added, and employers are now obliged to provide valid reasons for dismissals. Amanawa (2023) found a positive relationship between compliance with labor laws and the reduction of involuntarily forced resignations, unjustified resignations without compensation, and mutually agreed resignations concluding that compliance with labor laws is a tool that organizations can use to reduce their burden.

As can be seen, it can be said that remote workers generally have a perception of job security in both quantitative and qualitative methods. This can be explained by the working conditions provided by their organizations, years of experience, qualification levels, and positions.

7. Theoretical Implications

The theoretical contribution of this study is to reveal the relationship between remote working and the concept of job security and to contribute to the gap in the literature on the perceptions of job security of remote workers.

8. Practical Implications

Practical contribution is that the perception of job security is personal and that the perception of job security is formed depending on workplace practices rather than working models. When organizations strive for a positive perception of job security for their employees, they will encounter results such as increased productivity and performance and reduced court costs. For this reason, organizations that want to gain a competitive advantage in today's competitive conditions should consider flexible working models and the concept of job security and implement the assured flexibility model. In this direction, they should implement the necessary human resources policies to ensure employees have positive perceptions of their job security. Human resources policies should be organized, transparent, lawful, and ethical. This section is not mandatory but may be added if there are patents resulting from the work reported in this manuscript. At the same time it can be recommended that organizations act according to the Labor Law in the exit processes to reduce court costs and increase productivity, job satisfaction, and performance that fair policies will bring.

The increasing prevalence of remote work models need to be integrated into human resources policies. When human resources management develops fair, transparent, ethical policies for remote workers and eliminates implementation issues, employees' perception of job security will be positively impacted. Therefore, positive perception will lead to productive and satisfied employees. Desired outcomes such as employee engagement and satisfaction will also emerge based on these policies.

9. Limitations and Future Research Directions

Since a great number of the participants held managerial positions, it can be said that they evaluated the research from an institutional perspective rather than an individual perspective. Remote work opportunities were not considered. The research was conducted with limited opinions of employees working in managerial and expert positions in the private sector of the Turkish labor market. Perception of job security is a subjective matter; different results may be attained when the sample size is subject to change. It is recommended that the study be evaluated with the opportunities provided to remote workers in different sectors. It is recommended that the study be repeated with individuals with different seniority, experience, title, and demographic characteristics.

10. Conclusion

Remote working, one of the flexible working models, has become widespread, especially with the

COVID-19 process, and continues in organizations that have adopted the hybrid model. With the flexibilization of working models, the problem of precarity has come to the agenda. Although flexible working models are claimed to be precarious, the study reveals that remote workers' perceptions and attitudes towards the remote working model affect their perceptions of job security. If teleworkers have positive work attitudes supported by their organizations, their perception of job security is positively affected; if not, it is negatively affected. According to the qualitative data, it was determined that remote managers' and experts' perceptions of job security were generally positive. For a valid reason, exit processes were carried out following labor law. Therefore, it can be said that the exit processes and practices in organizations effectively form employees' perceptions of job security. At the same time, this can be explained by the level of qualification and seniority of the employees. Moreover, it can be associated with the perception, support, attitudes, and human resources policies of the organizations they work for toward remote workers. On the other hand, different results can be obtained when the research sample is changed.

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